

SROC Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

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Ethno Complex Vrđnickska kula, Vrđnik

Radiotherapy of children under anesthesia

Predrag Filipović, MD Ivana Miskovic, MSc Physics

*Department of Pediatric Radiation Oncology
Department of Medical Physics
Institute for Oncology and Radiology of Serbia
Institute for Oncology and Radiology of Serbia
predrag.filipovic@ncrc.ac.rs; aainv.mm@gmail.com*

Jelena Bokun, MD, PhD

*Department of Pediatric Radiation Oncology
Institute for Oncology and Radiology of Serbia
bokunjkv@gmail.com*

Modern radiation therapy involves precise delivery of the desired dose to the region of interest with maximum sparing of the surrounding healthy tissues. Modern techniques require great precision, and the patient's time spent on the linear accelerator is longer. Therefore, there is a greater need for anesthesia in all children in whom it is not possible to achieve that the child lies motionless for the period of time that is required for the conduction of a radiotherapy fraction. The pediatric radiotherapy and oncology team has all the medical profiles necessary for radiotherapy under anesthesia. In children under the age of 3, anesthesia during radiation therapy is often necessary. The anesthesiological approach is determined based on international recommendations, with the emphasis on the education of anesthesiologists regarding the needs of radiotherapy and oncology. The specificity is that the anesthesiology team leaves the patient in the radiotherapy bunker, and the monitoring is done from the command room. The anesthesiologist has experience in the selection and monitoring of the patient, as well as the ability to react quickly and adequately if the need arises. The role of the anesthesiologist is to carry out a pre-therapeutic assessment of the child, choose an adequate type of anesthesia and to take care of the patient after anesthesia. The goals of anesthesia in radiotherapy are the immobilization of the child, rapid sedation, hypnosis, amnesia, analgesia, shortest possible duration of anesthesia, and the rapid recovery of the child.

Keywords: radiotherapy, technique, pediatric, anesthesiologist

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